

Interview Guide – Expert Interview for the Validation of Attributes in a Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE)

Interviewpartner:

Unternehmen:

Datum:

Interviewer:

Dear Mr./Ms. [Name],

Thank you very much for taking the time to participate in this interview. The conversation takes place in the context of my Master's thesis at FH BFI Vienna and is embedded in the PhD project of Denise Beil (University of Antwerp).

Brief description of the Master's thesis:

The focus is on the empirical preparation of a stated preference Discrete Choice Experiment (DCE) to analyse decision-making behaviour in European freight transport along the TEN-T Rhine–Danube Corridor.

Objectives of the interview:

- To collect realistic and practice-oriented value ranges for key transport attributes (cost, transit time, reliability, frequency).
- To understand how shippers and logistics service providers evaluate trade-offs between these criteria.
- To empirically delimit the relevant value ranges (min–max) for the attributes and modes of transport (road, rail, inland waterways) along selected OD routes.
- To validate the composition, interpretation, and relevance of the attributes.
- To identify decision logic and thresholds for the later modelling of DCE choice sets.

Procedure:

The interview is semi-structured and lasts approximately 60 minutes. It includes tables for quantitative assessments as well as open-ended questions regarding practical relevance and interpretation. Ideally, the tables are completed in advance. All information will be treated confidentially and used exclusively in anonymised form for scientific purposes.

We look forward to your insights and your valuable practical experience!

Henrike Bauer & Denise Beil

1. Unternehmensmerkmale (Demographischer Kontext)

Ziel: Kontrolle struktureller Einflussfaktoren für spätere Modellierungen (Heterogenität)

- Unternehmenstyp (Verlader, Handel, LSP, Carrier, Sonstiges): _____
- Unternehmensgröße (Mitarbeiterzahl, Umsatzklasse, Standorte): _____

- Position des Interviewten (strategisch/operativ, Disposition, Management):

- Hauptkunden (Industrie, Handel, 3PL, etc.): _____
- Häufigkeit grenzüberschreitender Transporte im TEN-T Rhine-Danube-Korridor:

2. Kontext-Screening: Nutzung von OD-Routen und Verkehrsträgern

Ziel: Sicherstellen, dass alle fünf vordefinierten DCE-Routen im Interview abgedeckt werden.

Mit welchen der folgenden OD-Routen sind Sie vertraut oder haben Sie aktiv genutzt? Welcher Verkehrsträger wird pro Route regelmäßig genutzt?

Route	Verbindung	Länder	Aktiv genutzt? (Ja/Nein)	Hauptverkehrsträger (Straße/Schiene/Binnenwasserstraße)
R1	Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (via Stuttgart/München)	FR, DE, AT		
R2	München/Nürnberg – Praha – Žilina – Košice	DE, CZ, SK		
R3	München/Nürnberg – Wien/Bratislava	DE, AT, SK		
R4	Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara	AT, SK, HU, RO		
R5	Wien/Bratislava – Constanța	AT, SK, HU, RO		

3. Data Basis for the DCE: Empirical Attribute Assessment – Definition of Attributes & Guide for Interviewees

In this interview, all questions on transport cost, transit time, reliability, and frequency refer to the complete door-to-door transport process between two company locations along the defined routes.

For rail and inland waterway transport, we consider intermodal freight transport with containerised load units, i.e., including pre- and post-haulage by truck.

For road transport, by contrast, we assume conventional road freight operations, i.e., continuous direct transport without transshipment – door-to-door.

Our aim is to ensure that all information provided is comparable across the complete transport chain, regardless of the mode.

- **Transport costs:** Please refer your information on transport costs – where possible – to the entire door-to-door transport. Approximate values and ranges in €/tonne-kilometre are also helpful.
- **Transit time:** Refers to the typical transport duration from loading at the sender to unloading at the recipient – i.e., the full door-to-door time.
- **Reliability:** Refers to the share of transports that arrive within the agreed time window.
- **Frequency:** Represents flexibility and indicates the realistically possible number of shipments per week on a given relation – irrespective of how many actually take place.

Why extreme values are included:

Extreme values (e.g., for cost, time, or reliability) reflect rare but real situations – such as extreme low water levels, major infrastructure disruptions, or exceptional demand peaks. They help capture the full spectrum of operational realities and are essential for robust modelling.

Example: Studies and reports of the European Commission on transport corridors indicate that typical transport costs in European rail freight range between €0.04 and €0.08 per tonne-kilometre. In exceptional cases – particularly on long, complex, or heavily disrupted routes – values of up to €0.12–0.15 €/tkm have been observed (IRG-Rail, 2024; UIC & UIRR, 2024; European Commission, 2023).

What we ask of you in advance:

Please review the tables for the respective routes and attributes beforehand and fill them in – based on your experience – with typical, minimum, and maximum values.

This will help us to discuss deviations from the literature values as well as specific remarks in a structured manner during the interview. All information will be treated confidentially and exclusively in anonymised form for scientific purposes.

We sincerely thank you in advance for your time and valuable input!

R1 – Strasbourg – Wels/Linz (ca. 650 km)

Attribut	Literaturspanne	Durchschnitt Literatur	Typisch (Praxis)	Minimum (Praxis)	Maximum (Praxis)	Extremwert
Transportkosten (€/tkm)	0,05 – 0,09	0,03				0,15
Transitzeit (Tage)	2 – 5	3				12
Zuverlässigkeit (%)	70 – 85	80				70
Frequenz (Abf./Woche)	2-3	3				

Zusätzliche Kommentare oder kontextuelle Erläuterungen (z. B. saisonale Schwankungen, infrastrukturelle Einschränkungen, regulatorische Einflüsse):

R2 – München/Nürnberg – Praha – Žilina – Košice ca. 850 km

Attribut	Literaturspanne	Durchschnitt Literatur	Typisch (Praxis)	Minimum (Praxis)	Maximum (Praxis)	Extremwert
Transportkosten (€/tkm)	0,05 – 0,09	0,03				0,15
Transitzeit (Tage)	2 – 5	3				12
Zuverlässigkeit (%)	70 – 85	80				70
Frequenz (Abf./Woche)	2-3	3				

Zusätzliche Kommentare oder kontextuelle Erläuterungen (z. B. saisonale Schwankungen, infrastrukturelle Einschränkungen, regulatorische Einflüsse):

R3 – München/Nürnberg – Wien/Bratislava ca. 550 km

Attribut	Literaturspanne	Durchschnitt Literatur	Typisch (Praxis)	Minimum (Praxis)	Maximum (Praxis)	Extremwert
Transportkosten (€/tkm)	0,05 – 0,09	0,03				0,15
Transitzeit (Tage)	2 – 5	3				12
Zuverlässigkeit (%)	70 – 85	80				70
Frequenz (Abf./Woche)	2-3	3				

Zusätzliche Kommentare oder kontextuelle Erläuterungen (z. B. saisonale Schwankungen, infrastrukturelle Einschränkungen, regulatorische Einflüsse):

R4 – Wien/Bratislava – Budapest – Timisoara ca. 750 km

Attribut	Literaturspanne	Durchschnitt Literatur	Typisch (Praxis)	Minimum (Praxis)	Maximum (Praxis)	Extremwert
Transportkosten (€/tkm)	0,05 – 0,09	0,03				0,15
Transitzeit (Tage)	2 – 5	3				12
Zuverlässigkeit (%)	70 – 85	80				70
Frequenz (Abf./Woche)	2-3	3				

Zusätzliche Kommentare oder kontextuelle Erläuterungen (z. B. saisonale Schwankungen, infrastrukturelle Einschränkungen, regulatorische Einflüsse):

R5 – Wien/Bratislava – Constanța ca.1350 km

Attribut	Literaturspanne	Durchschnitt Literatur	Typisch (Praxis)	Minimum (Praxis)	Maximum (Praxis)	Extremwert
Transportkosten (€/tkm)	0,05 – 0,09	0,03				0,15
Transitzeit (Tage)	2 – 5	3				12
Zuverlässigkeit (%)	70 – 85	80				70
Frequenz (Abf./Woche)	2-3	3				

Zusätzliche Kommentare oder kontextuelle Erläuterungen (z. B. saisonale Schwankungen, infrastrukturelle Einschränkungen, regulatorische Einflüsse):

4. Attribute-Specific Deepening

A1. Core Data on Transport Costs

- Are there specific framework conditions that influence your estimates? (e.g., seasonal or regional fluctuations, policy measures, operational restrictions)
- What determines the cost level on this relation? (Tolls Energy Personnel Transshipment Equipment Other: _____)
- How sensitive are shippers to cost differences?
(Very sensitive Moderately sensitive Hardly sensitive Cannot be answered generally – please elaborate)
- Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ from the typical value realistic?
(Yes No Depends on relation/mode – please comment)
- How realistic do you find the literature values?
(Consistent with practice Too narrow Too wide Not applicable – please elaborate)

A2. Core Data on Transit Times

- Are there specific framework conditions that influence your estimates?
- What are the main factors affecting transit time? (Border crossings Transshipment Timetables Infrastructure Capacity Weather Other: _____)
- Are fixed delivery windows required?
- How tolerant are your customers towards deviations? (e.g., ± 1 day, ± 6 hours)
- Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ realistic?
- How realistic are the literature values?

A3. Core Data on Reliability

- Are there specific framework conditions that influence your estimates?
- How do you assess the average reliability per mode on your relations?
- Are there significant differences between routes or countries?
- Which factors influence reliability on this route? (Weather Terminal processes Staff availability IT systems Coordination Other: _____)
- How do you define punctuality in your practice?
(Arrival on the same day ± 2 hours tolerance Pre-agreed delivery window Any deviation acceptable if consistent Other: _____)
- At what value does reliability become critical or lead to the exclusion of a mode?
- Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ plausible?
- How realistic are the literature values?

A4. Core Data on Frequency

- Are there specific framework conditions that influence your estimates?

- How many departures per week are typical/possible?
- How stable is frequency over the year? (e.g., seasonal fluctuations, capacity constraints, weather-related factors)
- Which factors influence regularity? (Season Demand volume Timetable reliability Staff availability Other: _____)
- From which frequency level is a mode regularly usable for you?
- Are deviations of $\pm 25\%$ plausible?
- How realistic are the literature values?

5. Trade-Offs and Decision Logic

- Which attribute most strongly influences your modal choice – and why?
- How do you weigh cost versus transit time? Are there thresholds that would trigger a modal shift?
- How important is reliability in your decisions?
- Which hidden/additional costs play a role? (e.g., storage costs due to delays)
- What role do political/regulatory factors play? (e.g., tolls, CO₂ pricing)
- Which change in attributes (e.g., -20% cost or +10% reliability) would realistically trigger a shift?
- Are there absolute exclusion criteria (e.g., reliability <60%)?
- How do you prioritise economic, temporal, and operational aspects?

6. Attribute Validation and Further Aspects

- From your perspective, is any relevant attribute missing?
- Would you participate in a pretest with hypothetical scenarios?
- Are there underrepresented aspects in the modal shift debate?

7. Influence of Cargo Type on Mode Choice

- Does cargo type influence your choice of transport mode?
- For which cargo types is the choice particularly relevant? (multiple answers possible)
 - High-value goods
 - Time-critical/perishable goods
 - Bulk/volume goods
 - No difference
 - Other: _____

Optional comment: _____

Wir freuen uns auf Ihre Antworten und Ihre Praxiserfahrungen!

Referenzwerte und Quellen

Alle Wertebereiche und Extremwerte basieren auf anerkannten wissenschaftlichen Studien, EU-Reports und offiziellen Jahresberichten zum TEN-T Rhine-Danube-Korridor.